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Challenges Faced by School Management in Transforming a Conventional Teaching Classroom to a Learner-Centered Teaching Classroom Using Active-Learning Pedagogies

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Abstract

This research is aimed to study all the challenges that a school management faces in an effort to change the teaching and learning philosophy from conventional to learner-centered approach using active-learning strategies. This research has also focused on the aspects of why teaching and learning strategies in schools need a significant shift keeping in view all the 21st Century skills and students' learning needs. Through this research the researcher has tried to communicate a burning issue which is also a general misconception around the world that student-centered teaching through active learning can only be followed in schools following Problem-based/Project-based learning approach. Irrespective of the curriculum, any teaching and learning philosophies can be adopted keeping in view the main objective of creating life-long learners. The scope of this research is quite huge as it encompasses all the important pillars of education, with school management at the top of the hierarchy.

Keywords: *Conventional teaching, learner-centered teaching, 21st Century skills, active learning, life-long learners*

1. Introduction

Background of the study

As per John Dewey, critical thinking is one of the main purposes of education. Education must help us to delve deep into the problems and find out their solutions. (Popova, n.d.). He also disagrees with the concept of one size fits to all. This means that every learner has a different ability and a different learning style which ultimately leads to different learning needs. The main purpose of education is not only to impart knowledge or information to the learners but to share social experiences with them. This concept leads to social efficiency. Moreover, the purpose of education is to become a life-long learner. Education is not the product of any input. It is the part and parcel of life. Last but not the least, theory and experience go hand in hand (Shawal, n.d).

I am from Pakistan which is a developing country. So far as culture and language is concerned, it is a diverse South Asian country. In my country, education challenges are immense. Pakistan was once a colonial state of the British empire; hence it is not surprising that many aspects of the society and in particular education derives its heavy influence from British standards of education and curriculum design. The subject matter whether related to language, humanities or even

sciences is heavily euro centric. Many subjects do not highlight the local history, geography, social and geopolitical issues etc.

Since 1970's, major curriculum revisions are just been introduced in the year 2020, with the implementation of a single national curriculum (Government of Pakistan, 2020). The country has schools which follow many different frameworks in private and public sectors and there exist a huge disparity in the quality of education based on social status and gender. There is no doubt that the education system has evolved with the passage of time. But most of the system is still based on rote learning and traditional assessment methods. Even in this Century, the purpose of education for schools and students is to ace the exams. Education system is quite elitist, with all the best educational facilities available to the affluent ones (Hunter, 2020). The irony is that even in this century, where we all are natives of this digital age, not only Pakistan is facing this problem but several educational systems around the world where external exams are the main focus for teachers, students, school managements and parents are facing this issue. The contemporary education system is still exam-oriented. We can't deny the fact that the education system around the world is still authoritarian in nature which follows an approach based on a factory manufacturing model where students go through a conveyor belt, they are being sorted, later on packaged and then finally labeled/tagged keeping in view as per their so-called intelligences (Goswami, 2016).

As a practitioner of a curriculum that is interactive and provides opportunities for the students to develop almost all **21st Century skills**, I became far more reflective of my teaching practices. This quest for knowledge led me to qualify a Diploma in Teaching and Learning from University of Cambridge. This diploma helped me to develop an understanding of learning, review my teaching pedagogies, purposes of assessment and evaluate impact of this learning on my future professional practices. The credit also goes to the system I have been working in. An **International Baccalaureate Institution** inspired by **Reggio Emilia approach** which complements **Project-Based-Learning** and allows a natural progression to **IGCSE¹ and IB² Diploma Programme**. Learning is a life-long process and not a product. Learner is an important part of the learning process. A learner is smart enough to lead himself through the process through critical thinking and with the help of his inquisitive nature (Talebi, 2015). I think that curriculum also plays an important role in allowing the teacher to teach students in a way that helps them in acquiring knowledge through a process that leads to active learning. Most of our teaching practices lead to passive learning which ultimately creates passive learners. The system, I had been working in, had been following a project-based-learning stream along with the IGCSE stream where teachers are responsible for the external exams and students feel an eternal pressure to ace the exams. Teaching and learning pedagogies in both systems were poles apart. During my professional development practices, my task was to teach the students following IGCSE stream (with external exams) in a way that they were preparing for their external exams but the strategy was to act as their facilitator and to develop the skills of deep thinking, research, to become more inquisitive and problem solvers. The group that I was working on were 9 in number and I taught them consecutively for three years in order to see the difference. Results showed that this group of students performed far better than the previous group of students who were being taught in a traditional way, followed by rote learning just to score A stars. This led me to do the research that why can't all the students irrespective of the curriculum can be taught in the same interactive way.

1.1 Objective of the Study

¹ Cambridge International General Certificate of Secondary Education.

² International Baccalaureate.

Our students are radically changing and so are their needs. Not only the resources provided for a certain activity need to be effective but also the class environment (Aidan & Murphy, 2008). We need to address and bridge the learning gaps in our society. For this purpose, every stakeholder must be involved in the planning that covers all aspects such as resources, aims/objectives and professional development. Unfortunately, the system that we are working in, has now defined learning as an outcome. Grades and results in formative and summative assessments are now considered as benchmarks for measuring the success of students (Porter, 2020). Most of the college graduates are either underemployed or unemployed because in a professional environment more than a Bachelor's degree, life skills are required. Life skills enable adults to function properly in society and include stress management, study habits, financial knowledge, self-care, social awareness, and the general ability to work well with anyone. This problem can only be solved through change in curriculum and a change in teaching pedagogies. This urges for a huge shift in the expectations of curriculum developers. Due to changing global trends, many countries around the world are considering reforms in their curriculum in order to make their children well-equipped with the competencies required in this modern era. Many OECD³ countries have been engaged in educational reforms e.g., Finland, Japan, Norway, United Kingdom etc. As per the research, more than 40 countries are now participating in the OECD-led Education-2020 project in an effort to explore the skills and competencies required by the students to develop. On one hand, it is a national issue and on the other hand it can be influenced by international trends such as competitive exams and globalization (Gouëdard, Pont, Huang, & OECD, 2020).

The concept of backward designing can also be used to adapt the curriculum as per the social changes. Curriculum mapping must be based on the concept that teachers are clear of the aims for their students, which then leads them to decide for an appropriate type and level of assessments which ultimately leads to a radical lesson designing (Wiggins, 2013).

1.2 Research Questions

Following are the questions that this study aims to answer:

1. What is the main purpose of education?
2. How important is curriculum and instructional design in transforming the conventional teaching system to the learner-centered system?
3. What are the challenges that management faces in transforming a conventional teaching classroom to a learner-centered class room.?
4. How can we make students life-long learners?

1.3 Significance of the Study

This study is significant in many regards. As it includes practical insights into all the aspects and challenges, a management could face in order to change the system from conventional to student-centered and what can be the possible ways to resolve this issue in order to develop all the required 21st Century skills in the learners and to make them life-long, reflective, and analytical minded students. This research is very helpful for all the educators who are the actual practitioners of the curriculum and who need to understand the significance of the active learning teaching and learning strategies. This will help all the managers and educators to think deeply and reflect on their own practices.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Important Terms and Their Definitions

Following terms are very crucial with reference to this research.

³ Organization for Economics Co-operation and Development.

Instructional Design:

Instructional design includes performance, analysis of learning, design, development, implementation and even evaluation. It is considered to be a scientific discipline because it is considered to be linked with the prescribed descriptions. (Seel, Lehmann, Blumschein, & Podolskiy, 2017). Instructional design is a systematic process, materials are continued and the process is mindful which makes Instructional design a science.

Learner Analysis:

Learner analysis is a process where we gather information about our learner based on certain characteristics. This is a very crucial step and must be performed before as an instructional designer before moving to the design phase. This allows us to choose materials wisely in order to meet the individual needs of the learners. (Wikiversity, 2018).

Pragmatism:

So far as pragmatism is concerned, this philosophy advocates the idea that truth is relative and one must be open to change and reality (Sharpes, 2001). I totally believe in this aspect of this philosophy and it is rightly said that the only permanent thing in life is change. We are digital natives and so are our students. The worst thing that we can do to our students is to teach them the way we were being taught.

Progressivism:

Progressivism believes in more engaged, experiential and student-centered learning. It has two aspects: Administrative and pedagogical progressivism. As opposed to pedagogical progressivism, administrative progressivism advocates the idea of delivering curriculum, social efficiency and social reproduction (Labaree, 2005).

21st Century Skills:

These refer to a broad set of skills, habits, knowledge and characteristics that are very critical to be developed in today's world in order to become successful. Communication, collaboration, creativity and cooperation are one of the few 21st century skills. (The Glossary of Education Reform, 2016).

Curriculum:

Marsh (1997) defines curriculum as "interrelated set of plans and experiences which a student completes under the guidance of a school". Such a quality curriculum enables and supports holistic learning while providing a bridge between education and human development (Stabback, 2016).

2.2 Educational philosophies that support the idea of student-centered learning approach that leads to active-learning.

Experiential Learning:

It is a process which takes place through transformation of experiences. Grasping and transforming experience forms the basis for gaining knowledge. (Kolb, 1984). Students learn best through personal experience. This not only enables them to think maturely and deeply but also inculcates the habit of self-reflection and provides an opportunity for problem-solving.

Student-Centered Learning:

Teaching environment must be more student-centered and teachers must act as a facilitator. Our knowledge as a learner primarily depends upon our interaction with people through communication. There is a theory based on two major ideas; neuropsychological and Second aspect deals with the fact that cognitive development is dependent on the Zone of Proximal Development: A level of development which is achieved by children when they get engaged in social behavior. (Vygotsky, Cole, & Steiner, 1978).

Social Learning:

Social learning theory believes in the concept that 1. People can learn by observing each other. 2. Internal mental state is also an important aspect of learning. 3. The concept that all the learnt things don't result in the change in behavior. People usually learn by observing others and then later on utilize that learnt behavior to perform their own actions. Not only external factors are always responsible for learning or forming actions but internal state of mind is another very important factor. (Cherry, 2019).

Constructivist Approach:

Constructivism leads to the concept that individuals/learners construct their own knowledge. This means that people build on their existing knowledge to learn new one. People also learn from each other in order to learn. (McLeod, 2019). One thing is worth noticing that learning is an active process. This means that in order for the learning to take place, the learner will have to play an active role in the process.

Inquiry-Based-Learning:

It is far more than letting students think about what they want to know. This technique requires the teachers to trigger the curiosity and in-depth thinking skills of the students. This is a complex philosophy, where the implicit goal is to facilitate students in inquiring and solving problems. (Gawron, 2016). It includes different aspects such as Project-based-learning, Problem-based-learning and design learning. (Barron & Hammond, 2008).

We are nurturing our students in an environment where there is cut-throat competition for grades. Achievement levels and capability of a student is measured in terms of grades. This competition is snatching emotions and empathy from students.

Research shows that educational experiences that are active, social, contextual, engaging, and student-owned lead to deeper learning. The benefits of collaborative learning include: Development of higher-level thinking, oral communication, self-management, and leadership skills, Promotion of student-faculty interaction, increase in student retention, self-esteem, and responsibility, Exposure to and an increase in understanding of diverse perspectives and Preparation for real life social and employment situations. (Cornell. University, 2021).

Backward-designing

Backward-designing is a very important concept which leads to the idea that the end objective must be in the mind of the management and the educators. If the aims and objectives are clear, this leads to the concept of how educators are going to get the evidence regarding the achievement of their objectives. Last but not the least the resources and lesson planning is to be considered. Whereas, usually in conventional teaching educators are bound by the resources and curriculum and hence, prepare their teaching material based on that. (Wiggins, 2013).

Backward Designing

Stage 1 – Desired Results		
ESTABLISHED GOALS The enduring understandings and learning goals of the lesson, unit, or course.	<i>Transfer</i>	
	<i>Students will be able to independently use their learning to...</i> Refers to how students will transfer the knowledge gained from the lesson, unit, or course and apply it outside of the context of the course.	
	<i>Meaning</i>	
	<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> UNDERSTANDINGS <i>Students will understand that...</i> Refers to the big ideas and specific understandings students will have when they complete the lesson, unit, or course. </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> ESSENTIAL QUESTIONS Refers to the provocative questions that foster inquiry, understanding, and transfer of learning. These questions typically frame the lesson, unit, or course and are often revisited. If students attain the established goals, they should be able to answer the essential question(s). </td> </tr> </table>	UNDERSTANDINGS <i>Students will understand that...</i> Refers to the big ideas and specific understandings students will have when they complete the lesson, unit, or course.
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<i>Acquisition</i>		
<i>Students will know...</i> Refers to the key knowledge students will acquire from the lesson, unit, or course.	<i>Students will be skilled at...</i> Refers to the key skills students will acquire from the lesson, unit, or course.	

1. Sample, Mark. (2011). *Teaching for Enduring Understanding*. Retrieved from <http://www.chronicle.com/blogs/profhacker/teaching-for-enduring-understanding/35243>.
 2. Wiggins, Grant, and McTighe, Jay. (1998). *Backward Design*. In *Understanding by Design* (pp. 13-34). ASCD.

Backward Designing

Stage 2 – Evidence and Assessment	
Evaluative Criteria	Assessment Evidence
Refers to the various types of criteria that students will be evaluated on.	PERFORMANCE TASK(S): Refers to the authentic performance task(s) that students will complete to demonstrate the desired understandings or demonstrate they have attained the goals. The performance task(s) are typically larger assessments that coalesce various concepts and understandings like large projects or papers.
	OTHER EVIDENCE: Refers to other types of evidence that will show if students have demonstrated achievement of the desired results. This includes quizzes, tests, homework, etc. This is also a good point to consider incorporating self-assessments and student reflections.
Stage 3 – Learning Plan	
<i>Summary of Key Learning Events and Instruction</i>	
This stage encompasses the individual learning activities and instructional strategies that will be employed. This includes lectures, discussions, problem-solving sessions, etc.	

(Wiggins, 2013)

3. METHODOLOGY

This research is based on qualitative study conducted in two schools. One in an International IB and IGCSE based international school in Pakistan. One is called TNS-Beaconhouse and the other one is an international school in Tsukuba, Japan named Liberty International school. This is action research which includes a wide variety of evaluation, investigation, observation, as well as analysis. The main objective behind choosing these schools was that both of these educational institutions have gone through this transitional phase. The data for this research were gathered through direct observations, interventions, and feedback and interviews were also conducted.

3.1 Research Limitations:

As the research approach is qualitative and is also limited to the participation of International Private schools, the generalizability of this research study may be limited to some extent.

As this research study involves all the important aspects of the system that are being influenced directly in the phase of transition. All of them have been involved.

3.2 Class Observations and Discussions with the Teachers:

The researcher had pre-lesson discussions and post-lessons discussions with the teachers. The lessons conducted in a traditional manner and as per the active learning strategies were directly observed.

(Lesson plans and post observation discussions have been attached in the appendix).

3.3 Direct Meetings and Interviews with the school managers:

Meetings had been held and interviews had been conducted with the school management in order to understand the types of challenges they face in the process of transition. There were post class-observation meetings as well which gave some solutions for the problems. (Interviews have been attached in the appendix).

3.4 Feed-back from students:

Feedback forms were being filled by the students and were used as the source to analyze the impact of transition. (Feedback has been attached).

4. FINDING AND DISCUSSIONS

Discussions and interviews with the principals of the school, its academic coordinators and curriculum development team gave researcher a proper overview that was the intention and real philosophy behind the whole transition. All the planning and ideas were backed by proper educational philosophies and practices around the world. The challenges that they were facing were immense in terms of implementation. It was not only the teaching and learning strategies that had to be reviewed but also the involvement and convincing of teachers, parent body and students was a significant issue. In order to implement the learner-centered environment, the whole management team had to be on the same page. To convince all the other stake-holders, they had to be convinced by the teaching and philosophies themselves. Curriculum developers had to be involved as well. An emphasis was laid on the fact that the curriculum needs to be flexible enough to meet the needs the learners of this century.

Although motivation (Extrinsic and intrinsic) and professional development for teachers was required, the strategy of "Learning by Doing" was being adopted to convince the teachers. Unless they had applied and noticed the difference that management was trying to convince them about, they couldn't have been the real practitioners as per the required philosophies. Unit planners were being designed. For this a team of all the full-time teachers had to be constituted. They had to plan the units horizontally in order for the plan to be applied in all sections of the same class. The same lessons with the same topics were being taught in a conventional manner as the teachers had already been teaching, followed by the active learning teaching strategies, which was the ultimate goal. A Constructivist approach was followed for designing the same lesson in order to compare and contrast the results, to see the level of student's engagement, their level of motivation, and the quality of work produced by the students in such an active learning environment. This practical activity was helpful enough to convince the teachers and also served as an eye-opener for them to analyze, revamp and to reflect on their prior teaching practices. This activity helped in realization of the fact that not only the teaching strategies but collaborative class environment where students stay active through collaboration and discussion is also very important. The irony is that the young teachers were comparatively easy to be convinced but the most experienced teachers gave very tough time in this regard. This whole implementation required a new learning perspective followed by the technique to unlearn the previous strategies and re-learn the required ones.

In the case of students, different strategies were followed to receive their feedback. The researcher took notes and directly observed the students followed by some class discussions. Teachers formatively assessed the students through different techniques. Students were

motivated to reflect on their learning practices and write reflection journals in order to see the difference of motivation and outcomes after following the constructivist learning approaches.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion:

“Curriculum and instruction are the very heart and soul of schooling”. (Slattery, 2013). Curriculum designing and instructional methods designed by the educators for their learners go hand in hand.

Reconceptualization of curriculum has brought an immense difference globally but the competition amongst different curriculum theories still continues and will be continued. Still a great amount of work is being done for the curriculum and to improve its efficiency.

Understanding by Design (UbD) is a framework for improving student achievement. Emphasizing the teacher's critical role as a designer of student learning, UbD works within the standards-driven curriculum to help teachers clarify learning goals, devise revealing assessments of student understanding, and craft effective and engaging learning activities. (Education, 2013).

5.2 Recommendations:

- Professional development of the teachers is the first and foremost priority to make educators understand the significance of a learner-centered classroom as opposed to a conventional classroom. Those professional development activities must be aimed to make teachers understand that they need to develop the required skills in their students. A few examples are:
- Pose relevant problems to their learners.
- Encouraging creation, creativity and high-order thinking through essential questions
- Apply different active learning strategies in the class. (e.g., reciprocal questioning, three-step interviews.
- Apply different peer teaching activities.
- Integrate ICT in their lessons to enhance motivation and make their students lifelong learners.
- Provide game-based learning platforms to the learners.

Throughout the teaching and learning process teachers need to make sure that they are conscientious of their role as a teacher in an active learning classroom.

1. Teachers must be an active part of the curriculum development as they are the real practitioners of the curriculum.
2. Curriculum is to be considered as a live document and must be revised as per the modern-day requirements in order to make sure that the students are able to keep pace with the modern world.
3. Backward designing must be applied, keeping the final objectives in mind.
4. Parents are an integral part of this teaching and learning process, they are kept updated through workshops and seminars. If changes are introduced suddenly, resistance to change will be natural.

Appendix-1

Teachers’ feedback form

1. In your opinion, how important is the teacher’s involvement in curriculum development?

Teacher 1 (TNS- Beaconhouse)	I believe that the teaching personnel must be involved in curriculum development as they are the real practitioners of the curriculum.
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Teacher 2 (LIS)	For meeting the objectives and for horizontal and vertical planning, teacher involvement in curriculum development is very important.
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2. Do you think that you are independent enough in creating your lesson plans and strategies/resources to be used?

Teacher 1 (TNS-Beaconhouse)	I am partially independent. Our school greatly emphasizes horizontal planning and communication amongst the teachers.
Teacher 2 (LIS)	I am quite independent in this regard as I am solely responsible for my students' learning.

3. From the scale of 1-10 (1 being the lowest and 10 being the highest) how engaged and motivated are your students in your classes?

Teacher 1 (TNS-Beaconhouse)	I will have to agree that when there is no ICT Integration or group activity my students are usually very less engaged. In the case of a traditional lesson plan, the level of motivation of my students is almost 4.
Teacher 2 (LIS)	5

4. If the school is going through a transitional phase from traditional to learner-centered classroom approach, what are the most significant obstacles that you will have to face?

Teacher 1 (TNS-Beaconhouse)	Social-constructivism and experiential learning needs time, effort and flexible curriculum. We are usually bound by the pressure of results of our external exams and syllabus coverage.
Teacher 2 (LIS)	Student-centered learning requires differentiated tasks and class requirements. It requires proper training and a lot of time.
Teacher 1 (TNS-Beaconhouse)	Social-constructivism and experiential learning needs time, effort and flexible curriculum. We are usually bound by the pressure of results of our external exams and syllabus coverage.
Teacher 2 (LIS)	Student-centered learning requires differentiated tasks and class requirements. It requires proper training and a lot of time.

5. How helpful is professional development for the teachers in case of this transitional phase?

Teacher 1 (TNS-Beaconhouse)	It is one of the most important things.
Teacher 2 (LIS)	Proper planning, motivation and professional development are required. This type of system is very demanding. This requires job security as well as intrinsic and extrinsic motivation for the teachers to implement this change.

Appendix-2

Following is the lesson plan as per constructivist approach (Active learning/ student-centered approach) that I conducted in my class. (After discussion and meeting with the teacher, in order to convince him to apply a learner-centered approach). This lesson plan is a series of 2 lessons.

Content curriculum focus:	Analyzing political discourse
Grade:	10

Overview:	Teaching and learning are focused on the analysis of debates and group discussions from political discourse. Both activities mentioned below are interlinked.
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Learning goals: Students will:

1. Pose complex questions for inquiry, research skills and effective listening.
2. Conceptualize diverse ideas around complex themes.
3. Analyze and develop the skills required for oral communication and argument building.
4. Analyze the contribution of collaborative activities towards effective learning.

Instructional objectives (Analyze debates through group discussions (Cognitive / Affective):

1. Explore the history of presidential debates.
2. Analyze debate formats and candidate strategies.
3. Analyze critiques of the presidential debates format.

Step 1:

1. **Class Poll:** Did you get a chance to watch any of the presidential debates in 2020?
2. **Create a collaboration board:** What do you remember from the debates you watched? Students will watch a video (CNN, 2015). that includes historical debates by various presidential candidates. Almost all presidential debates follow the same structure. Depending on their types and nature, debate formats are varied. Collaborating in groups, students will note down the essential elements of the debate and organize them.
3. **Comparison phase:** Students will watch a video (NBC News, 2019). that critically compares presidential debates and their various formats. In groups, students will watch this criticism video and will write down the important points. This activity will enable them to compare their own identified points from the previous video and the video intends to highlight the main criticism.

Justification/ Rationale behind the activity: This lesson is meant to serve as a tool for the students to examine presidential debates format, analyze current debate format, and think of the different ways that can aid in creating refined formats and to develop a final checklist including all the required aspects for an effective debate.

Instructional objective 2:

- Create a checklist to assess effective debating skills.
- Understand the importance of facial expressions and body gestures while in a debate.

Learning activity 2:

1. **Recall prior knowledge:** In their groups, learners will recall their prior knowledge (Elements and structure of a presidential debate) before beginning the main activity.
2. **Main activity:** Keeping the video in mind, students will work in groups to explore each candidate's platform and their key issues to their campaign.
3. **Developing a debating criteria checklist:** Students will enlist all the identified elements that are important to be kept in mind while delivering a debate/speech hence, making up a criterion. Developing a criterion is part of a group activity. Two important aspects will form the basis for creating this debating criteria:
 1. Content of the speech.
 2. Gestures and expressions.

Assessment: I used formative assessment (Assessment for learning and assessment as learning) as a tool to assess my learners. Through close observations and taking field notes I assessed them.

Appendix-3

This lesson plan also includes the teacher's comments as a reflection of her own work. This lesson plan is a classic example that was utilized to compare the difference in teaching and learning strategies applied along with the difference in the engagement level of the students.

Subject: Language Art

Title: Essay writing

Objective: Comparing 2 essays and identifying the components of a good essay.

Implicit objective: The objective of the lesson activity was to make students differentiate between a high-quality and low-quality essay and use the acquired knowledge later on for future essay-writings.

Class-activity: (Conducted in a traditional manner before the meeting) (Overview)

Before reading this unit, the way I had conducted this activity was that I gave notes to my students with the written components of a good essay. The notes contained all the characteristics and important aspects related to structure and contents a good essay must include. The learners' role was quite passive, it was more teacher-oriented and based on conventional teaching style. My expectation from my learners was to recreate a previously written essay keeping in view all the new rules/characteristics learnt.

For recreating this lesson plan, I have kept a constructivist approach in my mind.

The new lesson plan:

Session title: Comparing essays.

Learning aims: Read: Read the given text in the form of essays.

Comprehend and compare: Compare two different qualities of essays.

Create: Create a checklist.

Learning objectives: By the end of this lesson, students will be able to:

- Recall principles of essay writing.
- Compare and identify low and high-quality essays.
- Identify qualities of a good essay.
- Create a checklist criterion for essay writing.

Content and activity:

Students will have to compare and contrast 2 essays of different quality. (One up to the mark with all the important characteristics and other below average).

Making of an essay checklist: Students will enlist all the identified elements that are important to be kept in mind while writing an essay hence making up a criterion.

The checklist will be pasted on soft board for future reference

criteria	marks

Grouping: Students will be divided into groups of 3 (4 members in each group) keeping in view their abilities. (Mixed ability group)

Recalling prior knowledge: In their group learners will recall their prior knowledge (principles of writing an essay) before beginning the main activity.

Differentiation: Content differentiation will be used. Each group will be given different essays.

Assessment as learning: Students will assess each other and will comment on or correct each other while discussing and comparing essays.

Assessment for learning: I will be assessing students through close observation and taking notes.

Exit card: (Formative assessment) Exit cards based on:

1. What I used to think about essay writing.
2. Now what I think about essay writing.

Teacher's Reflection:

Understanding by design is a planning framework which led me to design my planner. Backward designing was the key which helped me to design my lesson, my formative assessments, activities and resources to be used accordingly. This planning framework enabled me to decide in advance which approaches to teaching and learning to be used in order to achieve the required objectives.

This framework totally prepared me for teachable moments. Using constructivist classroom approach and to avoid a typical traditional teaching style was first and foremost priority. I had planned the lesson proactively in order to meet the needs of my learners individually and in groups. Inclusive approach w me to overcome the resistance to learning. It also helps the students to overcome their mental barriers.

Appendix-4

This includes the forms created for pre-observation discussion, observation of the lesson itself by the researcher and post-observation discussion and record along with the students’ feedback forms after the class was being conducted.

Observation feedback form

Teachers taught two sequential lessons which were observed by the researcher. This form is designed to support the observation process for each lesson.

Teacher name		Lesson observation 1 / 2	
Observer name		Job title of observer/Researcher	

1. Pre-observation discussion*

Pre – observation discussion date	
Intended outcomes of the observation – to be agreed between teacher and researcher. These need to be specific and measurable.	
Agreed focus for the observation – you need to ensure that some of the key questions stated are covered in your discussion.	<i>What teaching methods and learning activities will be used to help the learners achieve the learning aims and objectives? Why have these been selected?</i>
Does this focus link to a previous observation target?	Yes / No

* Section 1 is to be completed jointly by the teacher and the observer/researcher.

Date of lesson		Lesson topic	
Location of lesson	classroom	Age of learners	
Number in class		Lesson observation 1 / 2	Support assistants? Yes / No

2. Observation Record*

Teaching <i>This account should be analytical, not descriptive. The teaching methods being used need to be identified and evaluated. The researcher should focus on the areas noted in the pre- observation discussion</i>	Learning <i>This account should be analytical, not descriptive. The researcher needs to identify what learning is taking place. The researcher should focus on the areas noted in the pre- observation discussion.</i>
Key strengths <i>Based on the observed lesson</i>	

* Section 2 is to be completed by the Researcher/observer.

3. Post-observation discussion*

Post-observation discussion date		Location of discussion		Lesson observation 1 / 2	
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General comments and outcomes of the discussion <i>This discussion should have clear links to the pre observation discussion, to the observed lesson and to the learning outcomes stated in the syllabus.</i>	
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* Section 3 is to be completed jointly by the teacher and the researcher.

Summary of Feedback from Learners

Feedback from learners was taken in order to identify strengths as per the new lesson plans conducted according to student-centered approach.

Lesson 1.

Learner feedback 1		Learner feedback 2	
<i>Strengths</i>	<i>Areas for further development</i>	<i>Strengths</i>	<i>Areas for further development</i>

Lesson 2.

Learner feedback 3		Learner feedback 4	
<i>Strengths</i>	<i>Areas for further development</i>	<i>Strengths</i>	<i>Areas for further development</i>

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